

Edge Slot Waveguide Array Antenna for an Omnidirectional Radar System

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Abstract—An edge-slot waveguide array antenna is proposed to serve as the receive antenna in an omnidirectional radar system. The general design process for the antenna is described and the antenna is modeled in Ansoft HFSS and EMSS FEKO. Results from these simulations are compared with prototype measurements to characterize the antenna. The results indicate an $S_{11} < -10$ dB bandwidth of 6.5%, half-power beamwidth of 14° in azimuth and 96° in elevation and a realized gain of 12.65 dBi.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is strong interest in the development of lightweight, man-portable sensors to provide persistent surveillance in urban clutter environments. Many recent compact radar systems employ rapid scanning of transmit (TX) and receive (RX) beams to achieve this goal [1]. Significant reduction of system cost, complexity and size may be achieved by eliminating the need for physical and/or electronic scanning of the radar. One such proposed system employs a single omnidirectional TX antenna and multiple RX antennas with wide azimuth and narrow elevation half-power beamwidth (HPBW) and high gain to provide omnidirectional persistent surveillance. A monopulse radar and interferometric technique is employed for azimuth/range estimation. In order to optimize the results of this technique, the distance between phase fronts of neighboring RX antennas must be minimized by keeping the physical depth of the antenna design as small as possible. This presents a considerable design challenge since the realized gain must be maintained at ~ 12 dBi. An edge slot waveguide array antenna [2-4] has been developed to meet these system requirements of high gain and minimized antenna depth.

II. DESIGN

An edge slot waveguide array antenna consists of a section of waveguide cut to a desired length with an array of inclined slots cut into the narrow wall of one side of the waveguide. The antenna is typically fed with a coaxial-to-waveguide adapter on one end and is terminated with either a short circuit (metallic plate) or 50Ω load on the opposite end. When the antenna is terminated with a metallic short cap, the spacing, incline, and depth of the resonant slots become critical to achieving the desired resonant frequency [3]. The slots are spaced approximately $\lambda_g/2$ apart, where λ_g is the waveguide wavelength, and the first slot is spaced $\lambda_g/4$ from the end cap. The input impedance is dependent upon the conductance of

each of the resonant slots. It has been analytically determined that the optimal slot depth for resonance with a 50Ω feed may be determined from the slot width, w , depth, δ , angle, α , waveguide width, a , and wall thickness, t , as follows [3],

$$\delta = 0.23125\lambda_0 - \frac{a}{2\cos(\alpha)} + 2t \quad (1)$$

The design process for an edge-slot waveguide antenna is detailed in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Edge slot waveguide array antenna design.

III. SIMULATION AND MEASUREMENT

The design shown in Fig. 1 was modeled and simulated using both *Ansoft HFSS* and *EMSS FEKO* software with the specific goal of adjusting the dimensions, angles and depths of the resonant slots in order to optimize antenna center frequency and gain. Prototypes were fabricated using waveguide tubing with a metallic short end cap attached to one end and an SMA-to-waveguide adapter attached for the feed.

A comparison of the simulated and measured reflection coefficient for this design is shown in Fig 2. For operational security purposes, the results are generalized for a desired center frequency, f_c . The center frequency was accurately predicted by both HFSS and FEKO simulations to within 0.5%.

The measured $S_{11} < -10$ dB bandwidth was $\sim 6.5\%$, which was very accurately predicted by FEKO to within 0.1%. The HFSS simulation results produced a slightly narrower bandwidth prediction than that of the measured results or FEKO simulation. This is likely due to the fact that the FEKO model was very close to the actual prototype, with the full SMA-to-waveguide adapter easily modeled without considerable added memory resources, while a simplified waveport feed approximation was used for the HFSS model. However, even with this approximated feed, the HFSS simulation predicts the beamwidth to within 1.5% of the actual value.

Figure 2. Simulated and measured reflection coefficient for edge-slot waveguide array antenna.

The simulated and measured radiation patterns for the azimuth and elevation planes of this design are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Both simulations very accurately predicted the measured HPBW of $\sim 14^\circ$ for the elevation plane. The measured first side lobe levels (SLLs) were ~ 16.5 dB down from the main beam. The FEKO results predicted both first SLLs to within 0.75 dB while the HFSS results predicted one SLL to within 3.5 dB and the other to 0.75 dB. While the FEKO results generally correlated better than the HFSS results to the measured data over the full pattern, both simulations became less accurate beyond $\pm 50^\circ$. Better feedpoint modeling and finer structural meshing will likely enhance these results.

Figure 3. Simulated and measured elevation-plane radiation pattern for edge-slot waveguide array antenna.

Both simulations also reasonably predicted the measured HPBW of $\sim 96^\circ$ for the azimuth plane, which will be acceptable for the application of this antenna as one of multiple sectoral RX antennas in the omnidirectional radar system. The simulation results agree very well with each other while both tend to slightly underestimate the HPBW, each predicting $\sim 93^\circ$, or an error of $\sim 3\%$.

Figure 4. Simulated and measured azimuth-plane radiation pattern for edge-slot waveguide array antenna.

The realized gain was measured as ~ 12.65 dBi over the entire desired bandwidth and agreed very well with both simulation predictions. The measured gain fluctuated less than 0.1 dB over the entirety of the band. This important characteristic will ensure stable range tracking for the omnidirectional radar system.

IV. CONCLUSION

The design, simulation and measurement of an edge-slot waveguide array antenna to serve as an RX antenna in an omnidirectional compact radar system has been detailed. The measured reflection coefficient, radiation pattern and gain measurements of the prototype antenna will be presented at the 2016 IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society Conference.

REFERENCES

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